

Mercury’s perihelion advance from a speed budget

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We derive the first post-Newtonian test-particle Lagrangian from the observation that the isotropic Schwarzschild metric assigns every particle a *speed budget*: the coordinate speed of light is c/n , where $n(\rho) = 1 + 2GM/c^2\rho$, and the coordinate speed of a massive particle is bounded by this limit. The Lagrangian follows from one line of algebra, the effective radial potential from a second, and Mercury’s anomalous perihelion advance of $42.98''/\text{century}$ from a third. The derivation requires only the metric, the free-particle action, and elementary calculus.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mercury’s anomalous perihelion precession of approximately $43''$ per century was one of the first quantitative confirmations of general relativity [1]. The standard textbook derivation proceeds through the Schwarzschild geodesic equation in areal coordinates, where the effective potential acquires a relativistic $1/r^3$ correction [2–4]. The algebra, while not difficult, does not immediately reveal the physical origin of the correction: it arises because space itself is stretched near the Sun, so an orbit traverses more proper distance than Euclidean geometry predicts.

In this note we derive Mercury’s precession from a single physical picture—the *speed budget*. In isotropic coordinates the 1PN Schwarzschild metric is determined by a refractive index $n(\rho) = 1 + 2GM/c^2\rho$, and the coordinate speed of light is c/n . A massive particle shares the same coordinate speed limit: $v < c/n$ in these coordinates. The ratio $v/(c/n)$ —how much of the speed budget the particle is using—determines its kinetic energy. The entire 1PN dynamics, including the precession, follows from this constraint. (The “speed budget” refers to coordinate speeds in isotropic coordinates at 1PN order; locally, all inertial observers measure light at c .)

II. THE LAGRANGIAN FROM THE METRIC

In isotropic coordinates the 1PN Schwarzschild metric reads (see, e.g., Ref. [5])

$$ds^2 = -(2 - n)c^2 dt^2 + n(d\rho^2 + \rho^2 d\Omega^2), \quad (1)$$

with

$$n(\rho) \equiv 1 + \frac{2m}{\rho}, \quad m \equiv \frac{GM}{c^2}. \quad (2)$$

For a free particle of rest mass μ , the action is $S = -\mu c \int ds$, so the Lagrangian per unit mass in coordinate time t is

$$\frac{L}{\mu c^2} = -\sqrt{(2 - n) - n \frac{v^2}{c^2}}, \quad (3)$$

where $v^2 \equiv \dot{\rho}^2 + \rho^2 \dot{\phi}^2$ and the dot denotes d/dt . The expression under the square root is positive as long as $v < c\sqrt{(2 - n)/n} \approx c/n$ —the speed budget is not exhausted.

Expanding (3) through order m/ρ and v^2/c^2 (keeping cross-terms $mv^2/\rho c^2$) gives the 1PN Lagrangian:

$$\frac{L}{\mu} = -c^2 + \frac{v^2}{2} + \frac{mc^2}{\rho} + \frac{v^4}{8c^2} + \frac{3mv^2}{2\rho}. \quad (4)$$

The first three terms are the Newtonian Lagrangian (rest energy plus kinetic energy plus gravitational potential). The $v^4/8c^2$ term is the special-relativistic correction. The term $3mv^2/2\rho$ is the post-Newtonian correction: of this factor of 3, one part comes from the time-time component ($2 - n$) and two parts from the spatial component n [5]. It is the spatial part—the stretching of rulers—that distinguishes general relativity from a scalar theory and doubles the light deflection from Einstein’s 1911 prediction.

III. THE SPEED-BUDGET INTERPRETATION

The exact Lagrangian (3) has a clean physical reading. Define the *coordinate speed limit* and the *speed fraction*:

$$c_{\text{loc}} \equiv \frac{c}{n}, \quad \beta \equiv \frac{v}{c_{\text{loc}}} = \frac{nv}{c}. \quad (5)$$

Then the proper-time–coordinate-time ratio is

$$\frac{d\tau}{dt} = \sqrt{(2 - n) - n\beta^2 c_{\text{loc}}^{-2} \cdot c_{\text{loc}}^2} = \sqrt{(2 - n)(1 - \beta^2 \frac{n}{2 - n})}. \quad (6)$$

To 1PN order, $n/(2 - n) \approx 1$, so

$$\frac{d\tau}{dt} \approx \sqrt{(2 - n)(1 - \beta^2)}. \quad (7)$$

This is the product of two factors: $\sqrt{2 - n}$ is the gravitational time-dilation factor (the clock-rate field $\mathcal{R} = \sqrt{|g_{00}|}$), and $\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}$ is the kinematic time-dilation factor from the particle’s speed relative to the local limit. The conserved energy per unit rest energy is

$$\frac{E}{\mu c^2} = \frac{(2 - n)}{\sqrt{(2 - n)(1 - \beta^2)}} = \frac{\sqrt{2 - n}}{\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}} = \mathcal{R} \gamma, \quad (8)$$

where $\gamma = (1 - \beta^2)^{-1/2}$. This is the statement that the gravitational clock-rate deficit times the kinematic clock-rate deficit is conserved [6]. The speed budget distributes a particle’s “share of c ” between gravitational potential and kinematic motion.

IV. EFFECTIVE POTENTIAL AND ORBIT EQUATION

Restricting to equatorial orbits ($\theta = \pi/2$), the Lagrangian (4) yields two conserved quantities from the Killing symmetries:

$$\tilde{E} = \frac{v^2}{2} - \frac{mc^2}{\rho} + \frac{v^4}{8c^2} + \frac{3mv^2}{2\rho}, \quad \tilde{\ell} = \rho^2 \dot{\phi} \left(1 + \frac{3m}{\rho}\right), \quad (9)$$

where $\tilde{E} \equiv (E - \mu c^2)/\mu$ is the Newtonian-normalized conserved energy (obtained from $\partial L/\partial \dot{q}^i \dot{q}^i - L$) and $\tilde{\ell}$ is the specific angular momentum (both including 1PN corrections). Note the sign change: the $+mc^2/\rho$ in the Lagrangian becomes $-mc^2/\rho$ in the energy.

For nearly circular orbits, it is sufficient to work to leading relativistic order. Substituting $v^2 = \dot{\rho}^2 + \rho^2 \dot{\phi}^2$ and eliminating $\dot{\phi}$ via the angular momentum, the radial energy equation becomes, to 1PN:

$$\frac{1}{2} \dot{\rho}^2 = \tilde{E} + \frac{mc^2}{\rho} - \frac{\ell^2}{2\rho^2} + \frac{m\ell^2}{\rho^3}, \quad (10)$$

where $\ell \equiv \tilde{\ell}$ to the needed order. The last term is the post-Newtonian correction. Equation (10) is identical in form to the standard Schwarzschild effective potential in areal coordinates at this order [3], confirming the equivalence.

The orbit equation follows by substituting $u = 1/\rho$ and $\dot{\rho} = -\ell du/d\phi$:

$$\frac{d^2 u}{d\phi^2} + u = \frac{mc^2}{\ell^2} + 3m u^2. \quad (11)$$

The right-hand side consists of the Newtonian term plus the relativistic correction $3mu^2$.

V. MERCURY'S PRECESSION

The solution of Eq. (11) by perturbation theory is standard [2]. The zeroth-order orbit is $u_0 = (mc^2/\ell^2)(1 + e \cos \phi)$, with semi-latus rectum $p = \ell^2/mc^2$. The first-order correction adds a term proportional to $\phi \sin \phi$,

which produces a precession of the perihelion by

$$\delta\phi = \frac{6\pi m}{p} = \frac{6\pi GM}{c^2 a(1-e^2)} \quad (12)$$

per orbit, where a is the semi-major axis and e the eccentricity.

For Mercury: $a = 5.791 \times 10^{10}$ m, $e = 0.2056$, $GM_\odot = 1.327 \times 10^{20}$ m³s⁻², and the orbital period is $P = 87.969$ days. Equation (12) gives

$$\delta\phi = 5.029 \times 10^{-7} \text{ rad/orbit} = 0.1038''/\text{orbit}. \quad (13)$$

Over one Julian century (36525 days, hence $36525/87.969 = 415.2$ orbits),

$$\Delta\phi = 415.2 \times 0.1038'' = \boxed{42.98''/\text{century}}, \quad (14)$$

in agreement with the observed anomalous advance of $42.98 \pm 0.04''/\text{century}$ [7].

VI. DISCUSSION

The speed-budget picture provides a physical narrative for each step of the derivation. The Newtonian potential arises because clocks run slow in a gravitational field: a particle at smaller ρ has a smaller coordinate speed limit, so it “costs” more energy to be there. The post-Newtonian $3mv^2/2\rho$ correction arises because rulers are also stretched (the factor n in the spatial metric), so an orbiting particle covers more proper distance per coordinate distance and precesses. Of the $3m$ prefactor, m comes from time dilation and $2m$ from spatial stretching. A scalar theory that gets only the time part right predicts half the light deflection and 2/3 of the precession [5].

The derivation requires no tensor calculus, no Christoffel symbols, and no geodesic equation—only the variational principle $\delta \int ds = 0$ applied to the 1PN metric, and elementary perturbation theory for the orbit. The speed-budget interpretation makes the physics transparent: gravity is a position-dependent speed limit, and Mercury precesses because, near the Sun, there is more space than Euclid would predict.

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